

Translated instructions of the positive emotion interventions (English)

Focus on breathing

Sit comfortably for the exercise. Place your hands loosely by your sides, or rest your palms loosely and relaxed in your lap or on your knees. Your back and head should also find a position that feels comfortable for you.

Once you have found a position that is comfortable, close your eyes. Let your thoughts come and go like clouds in the sky. Breathe in and out a few times at your own rhythm. Breathe deeply into your belly. Feel it rise and fall.

Now, breathe in and out a few more times. Breathe in consciously and effortlessly through your nose and out through your mouth. In and out.

As you inhale, notice how your chest gradually expands. As you exhale, feel how your body gradually relaxes.

Take on a passive attitude. It's not about achieving anything or exerting effort. It's also not about performing the exercise perfectly. It's only about noticing what you are feeling in the present moment.

From now on, breathe in and out through your nose. Let your breath flow freely. Your breath comes and goes all on its own, in its own rhythm.

Feel how the breath flows through your body and moves it. Where do you feel these movements? The rising and falling of the breath? Perhaps in the chest? The belly? The shoulders? The pelvic area? Maybe in the nose or the sinuses? Notice where the flow is most noticeable. Keep your attention on that area of your body.

And as you observe this, begin to count your breaths. Count one on the next inhale, and two on the next exhale, then three on the next inhale, and four on the next exhale, and so on, until you reach ten.

When you reach ten, start again at one with the next inhale. Let your breath come and go in its own rhythm. Don't think about it. Don't try to influence it.

If it's comfortable for you, continue counting your breaths from one to ten. If you prefer, you can stop counting and simply keep your attention on your breath.

Stay focused on your breath.

And when you feel ready, return to the space in your own time. Feel how you are sitting or lying. Feel where you most notice your weight. Listen to the sounds around you. Slightly bend your arms and legs. Stretch and extend your body, and slowly open your eyes.

Take three deep breaths in and out.

The experiment will continue shortly.

Imagination of a happy moment

Sit in a comfortable position for the exercise. Loosely place your hands next to your body. Or relax the palms of your hands in your lap or on your knees. Your legs and feet are placed on the ground comfortably and relaxed. Once you have found a position that is comfortable for you, close your eyes. Let your thoughts come and go like clouds in the sky. Breathe in and out a few times in your own rhythm. ---*short pause*--- Breathe deep into your belly. Feel it rising and dropping. Feel yourself becoming a little bit calmer with every breath. Once you are still and calm, remind yourself of a situation, in which you were very happy. Try to perceive the situation in as much detail as possible.

What do you see? Are you surrounded by trusted people or are you alone? Can you see everything in your surrounding or is something hidden? Try to perceive your surrounding environment as precise as possible. What is in focus, what is fading into the background?

What do you hear? Is it completely quiet where you are, or do you hear animals or other people? Pay attention to every sound. Maybe the sound makes you happy? Listen carefully.

How does your body feel? How does your skin feel? Do you feel warming rays of sunshine or are you surrounded by pleasantly cool water? Do you feel wind on your skin or are you cuddled up warmly somewhere? Your body feels good. Enjoy the satisfaction, the happiness that your body feels so good.

What do you smell or taste? What smell surrounds you? Is the smell very perceivable or pleasantly subtle? Is there a taste that you can sense on your tongue?

Now take some time to integrate all these impressions. Once again dive deep into the situation that made you so happy with all your senses. Remind yourself of what made you so happy...

What do you see? What do you hear? What do you feel? What do you smell?

---*short pause*---

Feel the happiness and satisfaction that surrounds you in this situation.

Deeply take in this feeling and enjoy it for another moment.

---*longer pause*---

Slowly come back to the here and now.

Take three more deep breaths and then open your eyes. The experiment will be continued shortly.

Self-chosen happy music

Sit comfortably for the exercise. Place your hands loosely by your sides, or rest your palms loosely and relaxed in your lap or on your knees. Your legs and feet should be relaxed and comfortably resting on the floor. Close your eyes if you like.

You can now listen to the music you brought with you for five minutes.
We will let you know when the five minutes are over.

Reflecting reasons for doing sports

Sit comfortably for the exercise. Place your hands loosely by your sides, or rest your palms loosely and relaxed in your lap or on your knees. Your legs and feet should be relaxed and comfortably resting on the floor. Once you have found a position that feels comfortable, close your eyes. Let your thoughts come and go, like clouds in the sky. When you are completely still and calm, let your thoughts drift to a situation from your sport.

Imagine a situation in which you experienced great joy. A moment when you truly enjoyed practicing your sport. --- This could have been during a competition or training. --- Alone or with your team. Picture yourself performing your sport and the joy you felt in that moment.

--- *Pause* ---

Once you have formed an image, stay with the feeling of that experience for a few more seconds.

Now, open your eyes and pick up a pen. Your task is now to write down the reasons why you enjoy your sport.

Why do you like doing your sport?

Write down as many reasons as you can think of. You have five minutes.

--- *Pause* ---

What do you especially appreciate about your sport?

--- *Pause* ---

What are you looking forward to when you go to training?

--- *Pause* ---

What would you particularly miss if you could no longer practice your sport?

--- *Pause* ---

Perhaps it helps to reflect on the beginning of your journey in the sport? Why did you start your sport in the first place?

--- *Pause* ---

Write down as many reasons as you can think of.

--- *Pause* ---

The task is now complete. Put your pen down and read through the reasons you wrote for doing your sport. (How does this make you feel?)

Now, set the paper aside.

Take three deep breaths in and out. The experiment will continue shortly.

Writing down personal strengths

Sit in a comfortable position for the exercise. Loosely place your hands next to your body. Or relax the palms of your hands in your lap or on your knees. Your legs and feet are placed on the ground comfortably and relaxed. Once you have found a position that is comfortable for you, close your eyes. Let your thoughts come and go like clouds in the sky. Breathe in and out a few times in your own rhythm. ---*short pause*--- Breathe deep into your belly. Feel it rising and dropping. Feel yourself becoming a little bit calmer with every breath. Once you are still and calm, let your mind wander to a moment in your sport. --- This can be a situation in a competition or in training. --- Alone or with your team. Imagine yourself performing your sport.

---*Pause*---

Once you have a situation in mind, imagine the experience for a few more seconds.

Now open your eyes and take a pen. Your task is now to write down your strengths in your sport.

What are you particularly good at? What skills are you most proud of?

Write down as many strengths as you can think of. You have five minutes.

---*Pause*---

What makes you so successful in your sport?

---*Pause*---

What are you praised for?

---*Pause*---

What would your coach say about your strengths?

What would your teammates say – what are your strengths?

What do your parents and friends cherish about you?

---*Pause*---

The task is now finished. Put the pen to the side and read through your strengths again-

(What do you feel while doing this?)

Now put the sheet of paper to the side. Slowly come back to the here and now.

Take three more deep breaths and then open your eyes. The experiment will be continued shortly.